

CAMBODIA – VIETNAM – LAOS DEVELOPMENT TRIANGLE, POTENTIALS AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

The three countries on the Indochinese peninsula (Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam) have close ties in terms of geography, territory, as well as historical, economic, political, and diplomatic aspects... especially in In recent years, relations between the three countries have been consolidated and developed more comprehensively. Within the framework of ASEAN, the Mekong River Commission (MRC), as well as bilateral cooperation, the three countries have had many creative and effective initiatives and forms of cooperation. In 1999, from the idea of Cambodian Prime Minister Hun Sen at the Vientiane Conference (Laos), the Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam Development Triangle (CLVDT) was gradually shaped, marking a new development step in the relationship. cooperation between three neighboring countries. Over 20 years of establishment and development, despite facing certain obstacles, in general, CLVDT has shown its role as a driving force in the socio-economic promotion of the border areas of the three countries in particular, as well as creating a driving force for the development of other regions, as well as promoting each country

Keywords: Development triangle, Cambodia, Vietnam, Laos, potential, challenges

INTRODUCTION

Cambodia – Laos – Vietnam are three neighboring countries that have had a close relationship with each other throughout history. After all three countries were liberated and embarked on national construction and development, the governments of the three countries promoted cooperative activities to accelerate development. In 1999, at the Vientiane conference, the governments of the three countries agreed to establish the Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam Development Triangle in order to promote cooperation and promote the border economy of the three countries. This is a rather special area with many similarities in natural conditions, history as well as socio-cultural characteristics. Therefore, the construction of a development triangle will exploit the potential, strengths, and resources of each country in the region for the goal of fast and sustainable economic growth, leveling the development gap compared with other countries. other areas of each country, creating a driving force for the economic promotion of each country as well as the whole region.

More than 2 decades of establishment and development are enough to evaluate the development prospects and challenges that the CLV Development Triangle has been being and will be facing. In the coming time, with strong enough decisions of the 3 governments to overcome challenges and promote strengths, the CLV Development Triangle is expected to develop vigorously, promoting cooperation between the 3 neighboring countries neighbors, as well as creating a driving force for the socio-economic development of each country in the region.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is qualitative analysis, combined with synthesis and inductive methods, and explanatory research. The analysis process was carried out by using historical information and with historical and reading the text.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

About Cambodia - Laos - Vietnam Development Triangle

The Development Triangle was established on the initiative of the Prime Minister of the Royal Cambodian Government, Hun Sen, presented at the first summit of the three Prime Ministers of Cambodia - Laos - Vietnam in Vientiane (1999). Then at meetings in 2002, 2004, 2006, 2008, and 2010, the leaders of the three countries continued to affirm the development of this triangle.

At the second conference in Ho Chi Minh City (January 26, 2002), the Prime Ministers of the three countries agreed to prioritize cooperation in the fields of transportation, trade, electricity, and tourism. , training human resources and health. At the 3rd summit held in Siem Reap (Cambodia) on July 20, 2004, the three sides agreed to geographically expand the CLV development triangle (including 10 provinces), committing to increase strengthen coordination in mobilizing available and external resources for the development triangle. At the 5th summit held in Da Lat (Vietnam), the Prime Ministers of the 3 countries summarized the cooperation results and agreed to implement a number of specific contents: establishing the Coordination Committee for the Development Triangle. development, hydropower construction plan, agreed to build road 78 connecting Mondulakiri province to Dak Lak, route 18B connecting from Atapu to Kon Tum... At the 5th conference in Vientiane (Laos), on 26/11/2008, 3 The Prime Minister signed the statement "Elaborating special preferential policies to promote the strong development of the triangle area in the coming time", agreeing to accelerate the completion of the adjustment of the Development Triangle Plan to the end of the year. 2020 in the direction of linking each country's development planning and plans with cooperation in the Mekong sub-region... The sixth Development Triangle Regional Summit was held in Phnom Penh, Cambodia (October 2010). The three Prime Ministers exchanged and highly appreciated the cooperation results achieved in the socio-economic construction and development of 13 provinces in the Development Triangle.

The development triangle in the border area of three countries Cambodia, Vietnam, and Laos has a total natural area of 144,341 km², total population in 2008 is about 6.5 million people (population density 45 people/km²), accounting for 19.3% of a natural area and 6.1% in population compared to all three countries (Hoang Tho Xuan, Nguyen Ngoc Lan 2016, 9). Specifically: Vietnam, includes the provinces of Kon Tum, Gia Lai, Dak Lak, Dak Nong and Binh Phuoc with a natural area of 51,520 km², a population in 2011 is 4,663 thousand people, population density is 90 people/km²; in Cambodia, the Northeastern provinces include Mondulakiri, Ratanakiri, Stung Treng and Kratié provinces with a natural area of about 48,743 square kilometers. Population in 2008 is 684 thousand people, population density is 14

people/km²; In Laos, southern provinces include Attapu province, Salavan province, Sekong province and Champasak province with a natural area of about 44,091 km², the population in 2008 is 1,198 thousand people, population density is nearly 27 people/km² (Hoang Tho Xuan, Nguyen Ngoc Lan 2016, 153-154).

Right from the day of establishment, the heads of the three countries have proposed and agreed on operational roadmaps and appropriate steps to revive the potential and promising border area, towards the goal of “promoting economic growth” economic growth, poverty reduction, and socio-cultural progress in the Development Triangle area, on the basis of making full use of each country's potential and complementary advantages”. In particular, the specific goal of the triangle is to coordinate plans to build infrastructure, support the needs of key economic activities in the Triangle, and exploit the potential of agriculture, forestry, and tourism (Pham Duc Thanh, Vu Cong Quy 2009, 159); build human resources in strong industries; Create favorable conditions for the cross-border flow of goods, people, and investment capital within the Development Triangle...

On the basis of the summits of the Development Triangle, the heads of governments of the three countries reached an agreement on the working mechanism of the Development Triangle. Accordingly, the operation mechanism of the CLV Development Triangle includes the summit (every 6 months), the meeting of the Joint Coordinating Committee (JCC) (annual), and the Senior Officials' Meeting (SOM). Four working groups or sub-committees were established under the SOM, namely the Economic sub-committee, the Social and Environment sub-committee, the Provincial Coordination sub-committee, and the Security and Foreign Affairs sub-committee. The State Party appoints a minister as the co-chair and member of the coordinating committee. In addition, in 2016, the leaders agreed to strengthen cooperation between CLVDT and other regional cooperation mechanisms in the Mekong region, especially the Mekong-Japan Cooperation (Vannarith Chheang 2018, 8).

It can be seen that the Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam development triangle is a dynamic development area in many fields. The main areas of activity are Investment promotion; Facilitation of trade; Cooperation with businesses; Industrial planning; Small and medium enterprise development; Human resource development; Rural development.

Potential of the development triangle

Firstly, the Development Triangle contributes to promoting cooperation in the field of economy and trade between localities of the region, as well as bilateral and multilateral cooperation of the three countries. This is an area with many potentials and advantages for economic development.

The common feature of this area is a large plateau, located in the basin of the Mekong River, extending from the plateaus of the Truong Son to the Rattanakini Plateau and part of the Boloven Plateau. This is an area with a large land fund and a suitable climate for the development of industrial crops and the processing industry. This area also has forest areas and a diversity of flora. The triangle area between Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam is an area with a relatively large area, with a relatively rich area of forests and vegetation and animals.

According to statistics in 2009, the forest area in Laos in the triangle area is about 1.24 ha (accounting for nearly 70% of the total area), Cambodia is about 1.48 million ha (accounting for about 53.5%), Vietnam about 2.39 million hectares (accounting for about 53.5%). The forest in this area contains many kinds of precious wood (about 32 kinds of precious wood, of which 17 species are listed by the International Union for Conservation of Nature on the list of proposed strict protection. In addition to the flora and fauna in the area. It is also very diverse, including about 525 species, including many rare and precious animals recorded in the world's red book (Nguyen Duy Dung, 2009).

In addition, the CLV Development Triangle is an area with relatively rich hydroelectric potential and water resources. Many large rivers flow through this region, such as the Mekong, Sekong, Sesan, Srepok, and Ba rivers, bringing with them abundant water resources and reserves to serve economic development and promote cooperation between countries. country in the field of hydropower development and water resources. This is an area with great hydropower potential, on rivers in two provinces of Cambodia with an installed capacity of 4932 MW (such as Stung Treng, Ha Se San, San, Ha Se San 2, Srepok 1, Srepok 2 hydropower plants. , Srèpok 3, Sekong 1, Sekong 2...) belonging to 2 provinces of Laos with a total installed capacity of 3,131MW (such as Sekong 3,4,5, Xekunan 1,2,3,4, Xe hydroelectricity plants). Xu, Nam Kong 1,2,3, Xe Nam Noi, Dak E Meule,...) and belong to 3 provinces of Vietnam with a total installed capacity of 183 MW (such as Dakbla, Plei Krong, Se San 3 hydroelectricity, Yaly, Krong An, Dak Mam, Krong Pach...). In fact, the three countries have stepped up the exploitation of hydropower potential and strengthened cooperation on water resources within the framework of the Triangle as well as within the cooperation framework of the Mekong River Commission (Le Phuong Hoa, 2012, p.15).

The Triangle area is also very rich in mineral resources, including many rare minerals with high economic value. In Vietnam, the Central Highlands alone has more than 200 mines and ores that can be industrially exploited, in which the ore with large reserves is bauxite (reserve is about 305 billion tons). In Laos, bauxite reserves are concentrated in two provinces of Sekong and Attapeu with an area of nearly 300km², the length of the mine is about 3-8 m, and the content is quite high, about 41-51%. In this triangle area also discovered many locations with gold mines scattered in the provinces of the 3 countries. Particularly in the provinces of Vietnam 465 tons of gold ore. These diverse and rare mineral resources have had great effects on the economic development of localities in the region.

The provinces in the development triangle have specific strengths for tourism development, but they have not been exploited much and cooperation in this field is still limited. This area is one of the rare areas with relatively unspoiled natural scenery, with many of Southeast Asia's diverse ecological reserves. Many beautiful landscapes of the area are famous not only by tourists from 3 countries but also internationally, such as Yok Don National Park, Don, Yaly Lake, Bien Ho, Ngoc Linh Ecological Area, Church Buon Me Thuat, Queen Hoa Binh Library, Kon Tum Prison (Vietnam), Phoc Waterfall, Seponglay Waterfall, Pha Phong Waterfall, Sapien National Forest, Pha Lake, Xayxettha Pagoda, Phu Pha Pagoda (Laos), Preah Temple, Waterfall Phamith, Khorn waterfall, Viakchey national park... Some ethnic groups living in

this area still preserve their unique traditional beauty for a long time. The scenic spots along with the unique richness of culture among the ethnic groups of this region have become attractive tourist attractions in the region and the world (Nguyen Duy Dung, 2009).

Thanks to those potentials and strengths, the CLV development triangle area has had rapid socio-economic development. According to the report of the Ministry of Planning and Investment of Vietnam, in the period 2011-2013, 4 provinces of Cambodia achieved an average growth rate of over 10%/year; the provinces of Laos average growth of about 14%/year; provinces of Vietnam reach over 9%/year. For the whole Triangle region, the average GDP growth rate in the 2011-2013 period is about 10%/year. The economic structure of the CLV Development Triangle has changed in a positive direction, reducing the proportion of agriculture, forestry and fishery, gradually increasing the proportion of industry - construction and services. In 2011, the agricultural, forestry and fishery sector accounted for 49.8% of GDP, industry - construction accounted for 22.3%, and services 27.9%. By 2013, the proportion of agriculture, forestry and fishery sectors in the economic structure decreased to about 41.8%, industry - construction increased to 25.3% and services reached 32.9%. Due to the low starting point and small economic scale compared to the common level of each country, the GDP per capita in 2013 in the CLV Development Triangle area reached US\$1,340, equaling 76.6% of the average level of Vietnam, three countries. In which, the four provinces of Cambodia reached 750 USD, equal to 72% of the national average; four provinces of Laos reached USD 1,380, equal to 92% of the national average and 5 provinces of Vietnam reached USD 1,415, equal to 74.5% of the national average (Hoang Tho Xuan, Nguyen Ngoc Lan 2016, 9-10). This prosperity of the region has promoted economic cooperation between the provinces in the triangle, as well as between the three countries. The open and unified policy has facilitated cooperation activities in various fields... among the three countries in the dynamic Development Triangle region. In which, two-way trade between Vietnam and Laos reached 2-3 billion USD annually; Vietnam - Cambodia trade fluctuates about over 3 billion USD. Hundreds of investment projects by Vietnamese enterprises in Laos (nearly US\$5 billion) and Cambodia (nearly US\$3 billion, 2016 figures) show the strong connectivity of the three economies... (Thanh Xuan 2018). The regional development This will also create opportunities to expand intra-regional and inter-regional linkages and integration. If placed in the overall development of the Mekong sub-region, one can realize the special importance of this area: connecting gateways to the sea, expanding trade with countries in the region and outside...

Second, the CLV Development Triangle area contributes to promoting cooperation in politics, defense and security. The Triangle area consists of 13 provinces, which are important areas of the three countries. This is the crossroads in the strategic security position not only for one country but for all three countries in the past, present, and future. 13 provinces form a tripod, a very important strategic area in terms of national security. From the Tay Nguyen of Vietnam to Laos, to Cambodia, or to Thailand, it is very convenient and fast (Pham Duc Thanh, Vu Cong Quy 2009, 200-201). Provinces in the region are potential lands but have not yet received much investment and development. The area is also home to many different ethnic minorities. Therefore, the development of this area has an important meaning in ensuring the lives of people in the region, while also creating conditions for the implementation of the policies of

the Governments on the issue of ethnic minorities. religion, belief. Not only economic, but the development of the CLV triangle is extremely important in stabilizing the political situation, protecting security and order in the border areas of the three countries, and tightening the solidarity between the three countries people from 3 countries (Hoang Thi Minh Hoa, Tran Xuan Hiep 2012).

Third, the development of the Triangle area contributes to promoting socio-cultural cooperation in the border area in particular, as well as the country in general. The Triangle area develops in addition to the general characteristics of natural conditions, but also a very rich and diverse geo-cultural area. The reason this area is considered a geocultural area is because the indigenous people (indigenous people) here belong to two main language families: Mon-Khmer and Malay-Polynesian. In the provinces of Vietnam that share the border with Cambodia and Laos, there are ethnic groups belonging to the Malay-Polynesian language family: Gia Rai, Ede and Mon-Khmer language-speaking ethnic groups: Ba Na, Xo Dang, Gie Trieng, Brau, Romam, Mnong, S'Tieng. Meanwhile, in Southern Laos, there are also similar Mon-Khmer speaking ethnic groups such as: Talieng, Alak, Nghe, Xuoi, Ta Oi, Dru, Nha Hon, Xedang... In the Northeastern region of Cambodia, ethnic groups belonging to the Malay-Polynesian language family include Ja Rai, Rade, and Brao, Kachak, Kravet, Phnong, Tampoun... belonging to the Mon-Khmer language family.

There are even ethnic groups who have settled in all three areas of the three countries of Cambodia, Laos, and Vietnam. For example, the Jarai in Rattanakiri and the Phnong in Mondulakiri and Kratie can be found in Pleiku provinces and Da Lat city; the Brao and Kravet of Southern Laos also have close relations with their fellows in Rattanakiri; Ethnic groups such as Cadon, Xa Dang... in Southern Laos still maintain kinship relations with their relatives in the Tay Nguyen border region (Vietnam). It can be seen that with such an ethnic picture, the cohesion between the ethnic groups is very strong on both sides of the border, even stronger than the national cohesion (Pham Duc Thanh, Vu Cong Quy 2009, 202).

In addition, due to the diversity of ethnic groups, cultures, and beliefs in the border areas have mixed and interfered with each other. In the border area, most religions are allowed to operate such as Christianity, Protestantism, Buddhism, Hoa Hao, Cao Dai, Islam... Belief and religious activities are very diverse in terms of form and complexity in nature such as people on the other side of the border going back and forth from this side to live in pagodas, churches, and vice versa. Some ethnic minorities have had cross-border economic, social and cultural ties with their ethnic minorities who have settled on the border side from time immemorial. In which, social relationships are established through marriage, family, and kinship relationships between people of the same kin, or bloodline, creating a close and lasting bond, thereby creating the basis to expand cross-border economic and cultural relations between ethnic communities on both sides of the border. These contribute to the Indochina border crossing area that is very similar in terms of material culture and spiritual culture, creating a unique and rich geo-cultural area. Promoting linkages in the CLV triangle region contributes to promoting cooperation and cultural exchange in the border region, as well as between the 3 countries.

Challenges

Regarding objective factors, the Development Triangle has to face many external factors, especially those from big countries. This is an area with an important strategic position in the Indochinese peninsula as well as Southeast Asia, but it has not yet received much investment and development, so it is generally still very backward in terms of socio-economics. Therefore, major countries have had many investment strategies, influencing localities in the region. This process has both the effect of promoting socio-economic development, but also potential instability that threatens the development, as well as the connection between localities in the Triangle. Especially since 2013, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) was born as an anchor in China's foreign policy.

Through the "Belt and Road", China has made efforts to connect with continents and countries along the route in all aspects such as infrastructure construction, trade investment, culture, and tourism. political security, military, diplomacy, ... in order to create important corridors of economic cooperation, connecting Asia - Europe, the first is the dynamic East Asian economic belt, the other is The European economic belt is developed and in the middle are countries with great economic potential. As of the end of 2020, 125 countries have signed a cooperation agreement on the "Belt and Road" initiative, including several European countries. The Council on Foreign Relations (USA) estimates that by 2019, China has spent 200 billion USD on BRI projects and predicts that the number could increase to between 1.2 and 1.3 thousand USD. billion USD by 2027, making BRI the largest infrastructure development plan in history (Pham Thanh Hang 2021).

In the region, while Vietnam is relatively cautious with this initiative, Laos and Cambodia have enthusiastically responded. Investment of China in these two countries is constantly increasing. The most important BRI project in Laos is a 411 km railway connecting Vientiane with the town of Boten on the northern border with China. In addition to the railway, China has also invested in a number of power development projects, especially a series of seven hydroelectric dams on the Nam Ou River, a major tributary of the Mekong.

The dams, with a total investment of \$2.733 billion, are being developed by PowerChina in two phases. Phase I, consisting of Nam Ou 2, Nam Ou 5, and Nam Ou 6, commenced operations in May 2016. Phase II, which includes Nam Ou 1, 3, 4, and 7, is expected to be completed in 2020 (Le Hong Hiep 2020). However, many economic researchers have warned about the risk that Laos is falling into the "debt trap" of China. The World Bank estimates that Laos' debt level will increase from 59% of GDP in 2019 to 68% in 2020. Meanwhile, rating agency Moody warns of a "serious default in the near term", noting that Laos' debt repayment obligations for 2020 are around US\$1.2 billion, while in June 2020, the country's foreign exchange reserves stood at just \$864 million. According to the Center for Global Development (CGD), a Washington-based economic think tank, the main cause of concern is the tiny nation's ambitious plans for a railroad project. \$6.7 billion worth of high-speed speeds that China is looking to make part of its "Belt and Road" initiative. The cost of this project accounts for a quarter of the current GDP of Laos. A third of that will be paid by a Sino-Lao joint venture, of which the Lao government will contribute about 30%, or about \$700 million. But about \$480

million of that is a loan from the Export-Import Bank of China. Only about 220 million USD is left from the Lao budget (David Hutt 2018). This is a worrying sign for both Laos and the entire CLV Triangle region, as Laos' financial situation deteriorates, its economic growth and political autonomy will suffer. This will also have a great impact on the association bloc and the overall development of the trilateral triangle area (Heimkhemra Suy, 2020). Trong bối cảnh dịch bệnh Covid 19 bùng nổ mạnh mẽ trong khu vực, cũng như ở Campuchia sự viện trợ về vật tư y tế, thuốc men... càng làm sâu sắc thêm mối quan hệ giữa hai quốc gia.

Regarding the subjective factors, the localities located in the triangle are still facing many difficulties, there are many unstable political - social - security factors.

Most of the localities in the CLV development triangle are poor, underdeveloped provinces, even considered “low-lying areas” of the three countries of Cambodia - Laos - Vietnam. According to the reports of the three countries' governments, the border communes are all facing difficulties, so the governments of the countries have to come up with government programs and governments at all levels to support. As in Vietnam, the Government has implemented programs 134, program 135...but still not meeting the needs of people in the region. The infrastructure system has been invested heavily, but in general, it still does not meet the requirements set forth. The transport system is not only lacking but also seriously degraded, significantly affecting the connectivity of localities in the region. Lack of infrastructure, difficulties in attracting investment capital for production and shortage of skilled workers, in some localities the population density is too small.

Weak infrastructure and lack of human resources have always been a dilemma for CLV countries and pose a great challenge to businesses doing business in this region. At border gates and openings in the border areas of the three countries, the infrastructure is still limited and technical and commercial infrastructure is lacking, there is a lack of warehouses, yards, and equipment for loading and unloading goods, and the transportation system is still poor. There are limitations, some roads are in the process of being renovated and upgraded. It is difficult to travel. The transportation of goods is mainly by road, and the cost is high, so it has not been able to attract import-export activities and border trade.

In recent years, the economy of the CLV development triangle has made positive changes, however, due to its low starting point and small economic size compared to each country, GDP per capita in 2012 in the region of The new development triangle reached 980 USD, only about 77.5% compared to the average level of all 3 countries (Nguyen Quang Thuan 2015, 120). In addition, the border area of the development triangle has so far contained many unstable factors in terms of politics, security, and defense. In the border areas and inland, there are still organizations that oppose Vietnam and both Laos and Cambodia. These forces take advantage of economic and social difficulties in border areas to increase activities, and incite and entice people; associated with exile groups to oppose the government. In addition, in the border area of the three countries, there are also many evils such as long-term trafficking, gambling, drugs ... potential risks of insecurity and disorder in the area.

Finally, there are a number of other subjective difficulties hindering the development of the CLV Development Triangle area. The internal competition between the 3 countries and the whole ASEAN region, between the provinces in the Triangle, and other localities of the 3 countries due to the deep economic integration of the three countries into the regional and world economy. making the Triangle Area more and more likely to fall behind without adequate investment and application of special mechanisms and policies for the region; Some policies and regulations also cause difficulties for businesses such as regulations on goods transport vehicles, routes, on loan regulations; The challenges of smuggling, illegal migration, epidemics, forest destruction, and environmental pollution also affect the activities of businesses here; Management has many shortcomings. The management and administration of border trade activities is specific, but it is still mainly implemented in accordance with the general import policy mechanism according to international practices, so the potential and advantages of the border provinces have not been brought into full play. Meanwhile, legal documents on border trade activities are many but not comprehensive, overlapping, and unclear, causing difficulties for the management of state management agencies as well as the operation of border trade. business commerce.

Some solutions and prospects

Firstly, the Development Triangle needs to invest in building and completing infrastructure. This is considered one of the key factors promoting development. The infrastructure network will connect localities in the Development Triangle; connecting localities in the region with the political and economic center of each country and with the outside world. Because of those urgent needs, the master plan of the triangle area will have to focus on investing in the construction of connecting traffic axes, such as National Highway 13, National Highway 18A (in Laos), National Highway No. 7 (Cambodia), National Highway 14, 1A (Vietnam), etc. At the same time, the completion of the traffic network is also aimed at connecting the Triangle area with the seaport system of Vietnam such as Quy Nhon port, and Vung Tau port. Ro, Da Nang port, and Dung Quat port, promoting intra-regional and inter-regional goods trade. In addition, the governments of the three countries need to agree on the planning of hydropower plants so as not to affect the security of water sources and at the same time address, the energy needs to meet the development of the region's direction in the Triangle area.

Second, improve the regulatory system and strengthen the legality of the connection. The three countries Cambodia - Laos - Vietnam need to perfect the institutional system, create a synchronous, unified, and clear legal framework, and create favorable conditions to promote trade and investment cooperation between the parties in the region. CLV development triangle. At the same time, it is necessary to strengthen the activities of reviewing, evaluating, and monitoring the implementation of policies, laws, and cooperation agreements in the CLV Development Triangle Area. In addition, the three countries need to strengthen the organization and improve the capacity of the management and coordination apparatus for the activities of the CLV Development Triangle Area.

Third, promote linkages between localities in the region, as well as strengthen cooperation between the three countries and expand relations with countries outside the region on the basis of existing cooperation frameworks. Not only within the framework of cooperation in the Triangle region, Cambodia, Laos, and Vietnam also have close relationships with each other in many fields of trade, agriculture, industry, education, investment, and environment ... through regional forums such as Greater Mekong Subregion (GMS), ACMECS (Thailand, Laos, Vietnam, Cambodia, and Myanmar), Mekong - Japan, Mekong - Korea, Mekong - Ganges River, CLMV (Cambodia-Laos-Myanmar-Vietnam). The deepening and widening cooperation of these three countries is aimed at further strengthening the solidarity relationship within the bloc as these countries have mutual interests not only in trade but also politically and culturally. Giving each other special privileges both bilaterally and multilaterally further strengthens this friendly relationship. Expanding the scope of cooperation is also considered a recent mainstream trend in the CLV Development Triangle. If in the period 2011-2014, the cooperation of countries in the region was only limited to the provinces in the localities of the CLV Development Triangle, by 2015, the top leaders of the three countries wanted to promote cooperation and strengthen the connection of the three economies. It can be seen that the development prospects of the CLV Development Triangle are not limited to 13 provinces but will expand to neighboring localities, as well as all 3 countries on the basis of existing cooperation mechanisms, and integrated into broader cooperation mechanisms such as CLMV, GMS, ASEAN...

CONCLUSION

The Cambodia-Laos-Vietnam development triangle was formed in the late 90s of the twentieth century in the context that all three countries entered a period of strong integration with the world. The three countries have become members of ASEAN and actively participate in regional and international cooperation forums. The formation of the Development Triangle is an inevitable trend of the border localities, as well as the three neighboring countries on the Indochinese peninsula, in order to further strengthen the traditional relationship and create a new impetus for the development of each country.

Located in the border area, 13 provinces in the Development Triangle are all poor localities, with inadequate physical and infrastructure conditions, and backward socioeconomic levels. However, this is an area with an important position for 3 countries in terms of national defense and security. With the investment policies of the governments of the three countries, after more than two decades of establishment, the CLV Development Triangle area has made a strong transformation, making a significant contribution to tightening the cooperation relationship. cooperation between the three countries "mountain to mountain, river to river", maintaining defense and security in border areas. In the future, with its inherent potentialities, together with the investment policies of the three governments and the process of strengthening the operating mechanism, the CLV Development Triangle has more promising development prospects.

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